

and a pupa inside the leaf sheath from stubble of an unknown rice variety.

Evidence is insufficient to show that *P. orbiculare* and *C. dactylon* are alternate hosts; neither eggs, larvae, nor pupae were found on them. Possibly, the adult flies on the two weeds were only resting

between flights. However, *C. difformis*, found in almost all paddy rice areas around IITA, and ratoon rice plants, on which either eggs, larvae, pupae, or adults were found, could be host plants during the nonrice cropping period. ■

Soil and crop management

A convenient device for taking large undisturbed samples of paddy soil

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Soil scientists often need to take large, undisturbed cores of paddy soils for estimating bulk density or nutrient content on the basis of weight per unit area, or for conducting greenhouse

experiments with undisturbed soil.

A device for this purpose was recently developed at IRRI (see figure). The dimensions can be varied according to needs; we have also used a 20- x 20- x 60-cm version. The device consists of a box-shaped structure to take undisturbed soil samples and a sliding cover to facilitate removal of the bulk sample. Both parts are made of metal strong enough to gather and support the soil sample without distorting it.

To push the soil sampler into the soil, a block of wood is placed on top of it and struck with a sledge hammer. With the sampler at the required depth (as deep as 50 cm), the soil around it is dug away and the soil core is removed. Two men can collect a large sample (13 × 40 cm) in about 20 minutes.

Following is a typical example of data from Maahas clay (Aquic Tropudalf) collected at IRRI. The means are for 3 sampling depths with bulk densities computed for 9 cores, each 20 x 20 cm at the cross section. The high coefficients of variability are probably characteristic of the field site.

Depth (cm)	H ₂ O Content (% Oven dry basis)	CV (%)	Bulk density (g/cc)	CV (%)
0-15	84	9	0.66	10
15-30	56	12	0.91	6
30-50	57	12	0.84	15

We have taken 256 samples as part of a series of ¹⁵N balance experiments with no serious signs of wear on the soil samplers. ■

Diagram of a soil sampler designed to take large, undisturbed cores of paddy soils, IFDC - IRRI Cooperative Project.

CORRECTION

P.R. Hale. Two subterranean pests of upland rice in Papua New Guinea. IRRN 4:2 (April 1979). The correct address of P. R. Hale is Box 5144, Snowmass Village, Colorado 81615, USA.